

Discoverability Use Cases to help define Requirements for Research Data Discovery Tools

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Abstract

In order to build a better ecosystem for data discovery tools, we collected use cases between 2019 and 2020 from a variety of sources. We also detail the 'Actors' for these use cases and the 'Source' providing links, whenever possible. Since we found over a hundred individual use cases, we decided to cluster them to provide a better overview. We also did a small survey among data infrastructure specialists to find how they rate the importance of the clusters. We provide here an analysis of the use case clustering and the survey answers, while the collected use cases can be accessed at 10.5281/zenodo.5006524, together with the results of the surveys and the code used to analyse the collection.

Background

Findability is at the core of the FAIR principles, yet, researchers often report that data discovery is difficult (Chapman et al., 2020; Kern, Mathiak 2015). One of the reasons for this is that data discovery goes beyond the question of metadata quality alone, but also involves a diverse array of supporting infrastructure. As of July 2020, re3data counts 2542 data depositories world-wide with overlapping content. Data discovery is therefore not done by checking one repository, more effort is needed to discover data than scholarly literature (Curty 2016). Even within a single data repository, finding high quality research data with sufficient documentation for re-use can be challenging, as research data are rarely peer-reviewed (Callaghan 2015). In a rapidly expanding ecosystem of research data, it can thus be easy to get overwhelmed in the flood of data.

All of this is detrimental to the re-use of research data, with only 15% of research data being cited (Peters et al. 2016). This is not surprising, as the ease of discovery also plays an important role in researchers' willingness to re-use data (Faniel, Majchrzak 2013; Darby et al. 2012). Discoverability is therefore one of the key challenges for FAIR data: in many ways, we cannot deliver on the promises of this movement, if we do not increase the visibility of research outputs.

Most surveys on data re-use e.g. (Tenopir 2011) focus on why people share data, and not why and how people re-use it. Therefore, they provide little insight into the question we raised here: what are the data discoverability tool requirements? In a survey among 1677 scientists recruited from the Scopus database, Gregory et al. (2020) found that the most common challenge to a successful data discovery is unavailable data (68%), followed by distributed data (49%).

In a survey among 1.458 social scientists, Friedrich (2020) found that the most relevant success factors for data seeking are high quality data (94%), data that fits the research question (89%), data that is free of charge (86%), and good documentation (84%). Likewise, the most common reported problems are the lack of data fitting the topic (51%), the absence of sufficient data description (40%) and a denied access (40%). A large majority of users (80%) find datasets via literature search.

Gregory et al. (2020) confirms this finding (75% often use literature to find data) and discover an important correlation between perceived ease of data discovery and the integration of literature search with dataset search in their respective discipline. They also show that in the subsample of research support professionals, this number is much lower (42%), which may give us a hint that researchers and research infrastructure providers do have different perspectives and user experiences.

Data Collection

To identify which parts of the infrastructure are missing or insufficient, those which are working well, and to identify measures that can improve data discovery, we have compiled a list of use cases from a wide spectrum of disciplines and sources.

The use cases themselves follow the format: As a [role] I want to [goal] so that [benefit]. Most of the use cases were identified by the IN members, including researchers, librarians and infrastructure providers, or documented during focused events by participating contributors. One such event was the workshop “Data Discovery Across Disciplines” at Open Science Fair 2019, where members of the audience were asked to contribute. Another important source was the use case collection of the RDA IG Data Discovery. We have provided a URL for the source whenever possible. Altogether, over 100 use cases were collected. The spreadsheet is available at [10.5281/zenodo.5006524](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5006524).

Documentation

Table 1 Table description. Description of each column in the table, documenting the information intended to be captured from use cases. Note the use cases were ordered by Actor and Cluster, and colour-coded by cluster in their xlsx version.

Column	Description
A	ID of the use cases, these are referenced below and immutable to any sorting
B	Use Case: The use case in the form “As a [role] I want to [goal] so that [benefit]”
C	Actor: The role perspective of the use case, copied out for your convenience
D	Cluster: The name of the cluster (see <i>Method</i> and <i>Cluster</i> sections below)
E	Contributed by: Gives you the name of the IN member who entered this use case.
F	Source: The event or source this use case was found (see table below)
G	Closely_related_to: ID of use cases that were related to this one, nearly duplicates

Table 2 Documentation of the sources used

Shorthand for Source	Description (incl. Weblink, if available)
Implementation Network	These use cases were found by the members of the implementation network. https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/discovery/
Observation Study	These use cases were taken from Krämer et al. (2021)
Workshop	“Data Discovery Across Disciplines” at the Open Science Fair 2019. During the session, participants were asked for their use cases. https://www.go-fair.org/2019/11/04/workshop-report-data-discovery-across-disciplines-at-open-science-fair-2019/
RDA IG Data Discovery	The RDA interest group has collected these use cases through a survey. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1050976
EUDAT-Prace Summer school 2019	These use cases were collected during the summer school. https://eudat.eu/eudat-prace-summer-school-2019
DKRZ researcher	These use cases were collected from individual researchers working at the DKRZ (https://www.dkrz.de/), the German Climate Computing Centre.

Method for the Clustering

After collecting all the use cases, we proceeded to annotate them regarding the types of entities they referred to, e.g. Datasets, Papers, Persons, etc. Using these annotations as a guideline, two of the authors clustered the use cases thematically, with the aim to provide an overview of the over one hundred individual use cases, identifying common themes, and facilitating identification of direct duplicates or equivalent use cases.

We found six use cases which were almost identical, but having either student or researcher as actors (38 and 89, 57 and 96, 87 and 30, 39 and 90, 88 and 35, 40 and 91, see the *Closely_related_to* column in the source data). Indeed, most student cases were also valid for researchers, but we decided to keep the two categories apart to keep the original use case wording. We excluded five use cases (110, 23, 27, 25 and 77) from consideration, because we felt they were not a data discovery use case. We left them on the sheet, because some offered additional motivations for data discovery.

Our motivation for the clustering was to put together use cases which would require similar functionality from the data infrastructure and may therefore provide inspiration as to how the infrastructure may evolve. We tried to envision how the use cases could be operationalized. In rare cases when there was some ambiguity or overlap in the clustering, we assigned use cases to two clusters.

Clusters

Figure 1 Summary of use case distribution (left) and prioritisation (right). Distribution is plotted depending on use case categories (cluster) and actor. Six use cases were reported for both researchers and students, and some use case proposed for students may be relevant for researchers. Prioritisation of each category was assessed in a survey with 25 answers.

One of the largest clusters we found (14 ideas, counting duplicates only once), surprisingly, was on **data citations**: finding papers that cite the dataset, finding datasets that were highly cited, finding not only papers, but also other media (like slides, websites and blogs) that use and/or cite a certain dataset. This is surprising not only because of the inventiveness people had on how to use these citations (14 ideas in total), but also because there are only relatively few services that support these use cases and very scarce data in all domains.

Another large cluster (14 ideas) of use cases, the **overview**, does not have many services to support it either. Users suggested to have an overview of data by topic, by research question, and to help them with re-use. This includes information on very specific topics, such as micro-plastic and satellites, which were used as case examples; similar use cases are possible for other specific topics.

There were some use cases that would ask for additional **metadata** to enable **discovery** (12 ideas, counting duplicates only once). This includes many of the common metadata fields (such as licenses, amount of data points, format), but also makes a case for more rarely used or specialized metadata fields, such as experimental design, publication date and the precise instrument that was used to obtain/generate the data. Ideally, metadata should also be multilingual and use identifiers to facilitate cross-referencing.

Documentation in the form of additional documents is the focus of many use cases (9 ideas). It is invaluable for re-use, correct interpretation and should be kept closely linked to the dataset itself. Documentation does have some overlap with the data citation cluster, as documentation often comes in the form of scientific publication that have used the dataset before.

Many use cases addressed **discoverability** of the datasets (8 ideas). Here, users wanted to put their data into the repository with the highest discoverability, and get feedback on the impact of their dataset. They want to add annotations to improve discoverability of specific datasets. Developers wanted to maximize discoverability and one Actor wanted to make sure that everyone, including researchers from poorer nations, would be able to find the research data.

Convenience when using discovery systems was another cluster of use cases (8 ideas). In this cluster, we collected use cases that would make the life of users easier, such as visualization of molecules, thumbnails, RSS-type notification and autocomplete functionality. There are use cases for both an import and the export function of dataset entries, reminding us that not all users are consuming data, but some are trying to input data as well.

Other topics (6 use cases each) were: (1) **Linking** between datasets is relevant as well, both to find linkable, i.e. compatible, and similar datasets. (2) **Quality**, mostly suggesting that the metadata should be expanded to include organization or data providers to provide trustworthiness and note whether the datasets had been peer-reviewed. (3) **Cross-domain**, for enabling discovery between domains, e.g. through cross-domain meta search engines, links between topics, and crosswalks between different vocabularies.

Search **within the dataset** (5 ideas) is important for large datasets, e.g. the ones provided by the government, in biodiversity research or for climate observation.

Two smaller clusters that we nevertheless found quite interesting were relating to **Person** (4 ideas) and **Machine discoverability** (2 entries). Use cases in the cluster 'Person' refers to persons as entities, and aim e.g. at finding persons that would generate datasets of a specific kind, or as a combination with data citation, people who have published on a specific dataset. Machine discoverability was mentioned in two use cases, with the general goal to run algorithms on the dataset metadata.

The main actors in our use case collection are researchers and students, who have very similar, if not identical needs. There are two clusters that are different in this regard: **Discoverability** of research data is something that seems to concern data producers more than the researchers. Which makes sense, given that data producers have a vested interest in being seen, cited and re-used. The other cluster is **search within the dataset**, which is skewed towards domain-specific researchers. It should be noted that these are very different domains from very different fields, so that while the individual use cases are quite specific the general need does not seem to be.

Cluster prioritisation

After collating and categorising the use cases that had been submitted over the events described above, we wanted to ascertain their relative importance. We sought to extract a community consensus by using a survey tool during the GOFAIR meeting (February 3rd, 2021). We asked the attendees to answer a demographic survey (position, domain and geographical location) before asking them to rank the two most and least 'relevant' use case clusters.

For the participant information survey (25 responses out of a total of about 50 attendees, data also available at [10.5281/zenodo.5006524](https://zenodo.org/record/5006524)), we found that most participants hailed from mainland Europe (17), with 3 additional participants from the UK. Of those mainland participants, most were located in Germany (8), Scandinavian countries (4) and the Netherlands (3). There were 3 attendees from North America (2 US, 1 Canada), and 1 South American attendee (Brazil). Participant roles of attendees were

very skewed towards infrastructure providers (17), with 8 respondents providing data themselves. Seven people said they actually searched for data, though that was never the only selection for that question.

Most respondents were involved in Life Science (8), general science (7), or natural science (5). The social science (3) and computer science domain (1) were not well represented. Interestingly, when asked which tools were used besides a typical 'google' search, by far the most popular answer was the use of domain or community specific tools (10 of 21 responses). Of those responses besides community/domain specific tools, the most popular free-text answers were publications (3) or DataCite (3), and colleagues (2). All other answers were individual responses.

For the prioritisation of documented use cases, we pooled the two high and low priority answers into one category each, and plotted the number of times each cluster was indicated as being of high or low category (Fig. 1). Interestingly, nearly all use case categories were designated at least once in the low and once in the high priority group (apart from the overview category). There was a relatively high consensus for placing Discoverability and Metadata for quality assessment high in the priority list, while searching for data in a dataset or looking for specific researchers were both scored low priority in the majority of the audience. Unfortunately, we did not link the two surveys and cannot decipher if different target groups might have different priorities.

Conclusion

We presented here more than 100 use cases, categorised in 12 clusters and 8 actors. Interestingly, most use cases described scenarios that current infrastructure do not provide or provide badly. There is, of course, a certain bias in people trying to point out the deficiencies rather than stating what works, as a way to enact positive change. But it also reveals that there is still a lot to be done in the field. Our attempt at setting a priority list in these categories showed an absence of large consensus, even though most of the attendance comprised a unique actor, that is infrastructure providers. This suggests that a more precise analysis, probably limited to specific target groups, might be needed to set priorities in the use cases. On the other hand, it may well be that the whole spectrum is important and that one would need to satisfy most requests to create a tool that would be used universally.

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Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

References

- Callaghan, Sarah. "Data without peer: Examples of data peer review in the Earth sciences." *D-Lib Magazine* 21.1 (2015): 9.
- Chapman, Adriane, Elena Simperl, Laura Koesten, George Konstantinidis, Luis-Daniel Ibáñez, Emilia Kacprzak, and Paul Groth. "Dataset search: a survey." *The VLDB Journal* 29.1 (2020): 251-272.
- Curty, Renata Gonçalves. "Factors influencing research data reuse in the social sciences: An exploratory study." *IJDC* 11.1 (2016): 96-117.
- Darby, Robert, S. Lambert, Brian Matthews, M. Wilson, K. Gitmans, Suenje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Salvatore Mele, and J. Suhonen. "Enabling scientific data sharing and re-use." *2012 IEEE 8th International Conference on E-Science*. IEEE, 2012.
- Faniel, I. M., Barrera-Gomez, J., Kriesberg, A., & Yakel, E. A comparative study of data reuse among quantitative social scientists and archaeologists, Paper presented at iConference, 2013.
- Friedrich, Tanja. "Looking for data." (2020).
- Gregory, K., Groth, P., Scharnhorst, A., & Wyatt, S. (2020). Lost or Found? Discovering Data Needed for Research. *Harvard Data Science Review*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.e38165eb>
- Kern, Dagmar, and Brigitte Mathiak. "Are there any differences in data set retrieval compared to well-known literature retrieval?" *International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries*. Springer, Cham, 2015.
- Krämer, Thomas, Andrea Papenmeier, Zeljko Carevic, Dagmar Kern, and Brigitte Mathiak. 2021. "Data-Seeking Behaviour in the Social Sciences." *International Journal on Digital Libraries* 2021 1-21. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00799-021-00303-0>.
- Mathiak, Brigitte, Juty, Nick, Heger, Tina, Di Donato, Francesca, Jeschke, Jonathan, Widmann, Heinrich, ... Kraker, Peter. (2021). Stocktaking GO FAIR Discovery IN - Use cases, infrastructure (Version 0.9) [Data set]. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5006525>
- Peters, I., Kraker, P., Lex, E., Gumpenberger, C., Gorraiz, J. "Research data explored: an extended analysis of citations and altmetrics". *Scientometrics*. vol. 107: 723, 2016.
- re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. <https://doi.org/10.17616/R3D> last accessed: 2020-07-16